

Language and Didactic potential of Ukrainian for Specific Purposes Teaching forms in Developing Future Navigators' Text Formation Competency

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Abstract— *The article is devoted to determining the peculiarities of the organization of future navigators' text formation competence development during various forms of training on the basis of the analysis of scientific literature on language teaching methods. On the basis of analysis, generalization and systematization of scientific sources, we elucidated the forms of organization of language teaching (lectures, practical classes, seminars), which enable to improve the future navigators' ability to summarize, review and annotate texts that ensures the development of their textual competency. The conclusions drawn in the article can be used during theoretical justification and practical development of a methodology for developing future navigators' and marine educational institution cadets (students)' text formation competency.*

Keywords— *language teaching material, methods of development, teaching methods, text formation competency, lecture, practical class, seminar, speech skills, future navigators.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Introduction of competency approach into educational process caused focus shifts of its goals, objectives, and accordingly, the content: from the accumulation of knowledge, skills and capacities in the Ukrainian language for specific purposes to the development of students' ability to use them in practice, to employ individual speaking strategies and experience of successful speech situation in simulated professional activity and social practice.

The analysis of scientific works of the Ukrainian language teaching theorists proves that "text as a basic learning tool enables determining the tasks on all language levels, repeating speech-related information (determining the type, style of speech, ways of sentences connection within the complex syntactic unity, means of sentences connection in the text, finding a topic and comment, etc.). <...> It is the text level where the word semantics, its conceptual relationships are identified, where stylistic differentiation of coherent utterance simulation modelling is realized." [10, p. 61].

Today of great topicality is the problem of developing students' text formation competency. N. Holub, O. Horoshkina, O. Kopus, L. Mamchur, M. Pentyliuk et al. emphasize in their studies that text is a source of information, a product, a tool and object of activity; N. Bondarenko, L. Varzatska, V. Melnychaiko, H. Shelekhova et al. reveal the peculiarities of students' text formation skills developing; O. Hlazova, T. Hrubá, I. Drozdova, O. Karaman, L. Kratasiuk, L. Ovsienko, N. Perkhailo et al. determined the specifics of pupils and students' text formation activity organization. However, these works focus primarily on elaborating productive combinations of methods and techniques of pupils and students' text formation competency development or on elaborating the system of tasks aimed at developing text formation competency.

One of the main directions of higher education development is training competitive specialists capable of professional development, acquiring advanced knowledge based and information technologies. In this context, the problem of students', especially, future navigators' text formation competency development requires comprehensive study, since this competency provides acquiring communication strategies and tactics necessary for solving multiple life tasks in different situations. This justifies the necessity of studying language and didactic potential of Ukrainian for specific purposes teaching forms in developing future navigators' text formation competency.

II. AIM & SCOPE

The goal of the paper is to determine the peculiarities of arranging future navigators' text formation competency development during various forms of teaching based on the analysis of the scientific literature in language teaching.

We agree with T. Symonenko that "despite the large number of methods of implementing forms of learning organization, the commonly recognized is the following system: lecture (lecture-information, problem-based lecture, lecture-visualization, lectures- press conference); self-guided work (under the teacher's guidance, without the teacher's guidance); proseminar,

actual seminar, special seminar, seminar-research; other forms of learning organization (tutorials, clubs, colloquia, consultations, practices, study groups); practical classes, laboratory classes” [15, p. 200]. We will consider some forms of teaching future navigators the Ukrainian language for specific purposes.

One of the time-tested and relevant so far remains the lecture (lecture class) – logically complete, scientifically based and systematized presentation of educational and scientific material; one of the main organizational forms of classes in high school that forms the basis of knowledge in a particular scientific field, determines the direction, the essence and character of all other classes and self-guided work in the relevant discipline [7, p. 247]. This definition is the most reasonable and comprehensively reveals the peculiarities of the lecture as a classical form of learning organization in modern universities. In addition, we support the position of O. Kopus who regards lecture as a secondary scientific and educational professional text. It is important that during the lecture, students perceive a model text of scientific style, mastering in practice the text formation rules and at the same time create their own texts (notes). It seems appropriate to focus on building students’ skills of creating secondary academic genres that include the ability to perceive and analyze information, interpret it when taking notes.

We consider correct an opinion of A. Aleksyuk, that unlike other forms of learning organization, lecture has the following advantages: compared to textbooks it has much more opportunities to incorporate the audience’s specifics, latest scientific achievements; it does not only provide students with knowledge, but also teaches to critically evaluate the learning material; it facilitates the perception of information through the living word, intonation, teacher’s or lecturer’s facial expressions and gestures; it opens up the opportunities of direct contact of the lecturer with the audience that enhances their attention; lecturing saves student’s time [1, p. 457].

Without going into a detailed analysis of the peculiarities of university lectures we will make use of some generalizations of the Ukrainian language teaching theorists which are acceptable for working out the criteria of the efficiency of educational lecture on the Ukrainian language for specific purposes:

- lecture’s subordination to the goal and objectives of modern language education in Ukraine; lecturing focuses on developing future specialist’s language and communicative professional competency; motivation of students’ learning activity;
- scientific and solid character of the content, accuracy of formulations, clarity and consistency of presentation, arguing in favour of theoretical positions on the Ukrainian language with the examples of linguistic units, citing reliable information sources; providing clarity of presentation with modern electronic learning tools;
- mandatory inclusion in the content of the lecture of those problems which are the subjects of discussion among scientists and have controversial outlining in the scientific and academic literature. Teacher and scholar expresses his view on a particular issue at the same time giving students the right to choose any of the conceptions. But as a rule, students share the lecturer’s authoritative opinion;
- the content of the lecture should reflect the interdisciplinary relationships, predominantly those with special disciplines. Herewith, it provides mainstreaming of students’ basic knowledge gained in the process of mastering other courses that activates the development of professional competency;
- introduction to lecture plan of questions (with a list of references) required for independent study by students, and the questions recommended for an in-depth study of the lecture theme to students’ request beyond the curriculum;
- professional orientation of the lectures’ content, subordination of the lecture’s structure to specific didactic purpose; taking into consideration the specifics of the lecture theme when choosing methods of lecturing;
- optimal combination of traditional and innovative types of lectures within the modules of the disciplines; interrelationship of the lecture with other organizational forms of students’ classroom and extracurricular learning;
- lecturer’s consideration of mechanisms of and long-term and random-access memory: memorizing, storing, realizing and reproducing information (I. Zymniaia); use of mnemotechnical tools that facilitate students’ memorization of theoretical information on the Ukrainian language for specific purposes;
- teacher’s differentiated approach to the content and methods of lecturing, conditioned by the form of students’ learning (full-time, evening classes, distance learning), the discipline’s specifics, the theme of the lecture, the overall level of students’ success in the Ukrainian language for specific purposes;

- clear structure of the lecture, the unity of content and form, ideal verbal design, curiosity and vividness, normal rate of presentation [6, p. 209; 8, p. 151].

III. OBJECTIVE

The main objective of the lecture is to lay the foundations of scientific knowledge, to introduce the scientific research methodology of the discipline and yet provide scientific and educational interaction of the teacher and students [13, p. 3]. And in parallel students improve skills of text compression – “transformation of the source text with an intention to turn it into a more concise form, which is achieved by the omission of redundant elements of the utterance, elements that can be restored from the context and extralinguistic situation, and through the use of more compact constructions” [14, p. 43]. According to the observations, students perceive a lecture by hearing (full-time learning), and this perception causes most difficulties, or visually (distance learning). Therefore, we consider rational preliminary training students for creating a secondary text – outline, since understanding the lecturer’s speech speaker but not having the skills of taking notes students can not normally make notes. Thus, to teach students note-taking is one of the main tasks of teaching the Ukrainian language in high school [4, p. 273–274].

Modern theory of language teaching (O. Biliaiev, O. Horoshkina, L. Skurativsky, H. Shelekhova, O. Shunevych et al.) defined the basic types of notes and justified the effectiveness of exercises and tasks. We will only state those skills improvement of which should be continued in high school, particularly, in the perception of the lecture: to apply the techniques of text compression; to represent the sense structure of the text using the logical and structure schemes and tables; to present scientific and educational text in an optimal form for further activity and others.

We consider favorable the conclusions of O. Shunevych that to develop the skills of taking notes the following methods and techniques are optimal: semantic text analysis, observations on the language of the text, producing statements from previous training exercises, transformation, projecting; creative constructing techniques, algorithmization elements, condensing of linguistic units, analysis of their own and others’ statements, modelling [17, p. 13]. Some of them can be used during lectures on the Ukrainian language for specific purposes.

We agree with the conclusions of M. Hreb, that the lecture effectiveness depends on objective and subjective factors, including the level of professional competency of the teacher, namely: the possession of the lecturing methods, knowledge of factual material on the subject, a high level of speech culture and oratorical skills, etc. – and students’ readiness to perceive the information, development of a special hearing culture [3, p. 186].

Particularly noteworthy are semantic notes to which future navigators are involved when mastering special disciplines. Teachers of the Ukrainian language for specific purposes should rely on the principles of preparing semantic notes: discrete principle, according to which factual knowledge must be represented as separate utterances; the principle of finality, which implies that a set of utterances should reflect the knowledge of the subject in full; the conciseness principle, according to which the utterances should consist of a minimum number of words expressing a complete thought; the principle of the primacy of definitions, requiring introduction of new concepts through definition; the uniqueness principle according to which any utterance must not contain more than one notion; the unambiguity principle – each utterance is a semantic fact and must express only one idea; the consistency principle that leads to the location of the utterances according to the logics of presenting the course; the sufficiency principle, according to which any utterance is given in its full formulation, its sense does not depend on other utterances; the grammatical principle determines the subordination of the utterances’ structure to the logics of constructing correct speech [5, p. 105-106].

When developing the future navigators’ text-formation competency special attention should be paid to practical classes, whose purpose is to deepen and consolidate the knowledge acquired at lectures or using textbooks, to develop the skills of using knowledge, performing certain actions and operations [9, p. 103]. Modern theory of language teaching revealed the methods of giving practical classes in universities. We consider it necessary to focus on the functions of this form of studies organization: ongoing monitoring of the results of students’ self-guided work; students’ mastering the skills of independent oral presentations, justifying their position on the issue under discussion; teaching students the rules of discussing and skills of listening to the interlocutor; realization of communicative and activity-based teaching approach [15].

During practical classes students can perform analytical and synthetic text-formation activity: annotate and summarize professionally oriented texts, create their own utterances, review the classmates’ answers etc. Clearly, special attention should be given to the choice of professionally oriented texts. O. Roshchupkina considers them as a communicative unit, aimed at developing students’ specific skills at a particular stage of training. The text, the scholar argues, is a structural and

semantic functionally conditioned unity of sentences organized with the didactic purpose in semantic and content, linguistic and compositional sense that includes professionally significant for student information. [12, p. 71-72].

Preparing for practical class the teacher must take into account that students' activity on processing (understanding, realizing, assignment, evaluation, etc.) the text serves as a certain tentative basis for other activity and, therefore, is a structural component of other activities. Student's work with the subject content, based usually on a scientific text involves not reproduction, but active productive activity, allowing to translate the essence (semantic core) of original (primary) text to any other form of its reproduction. Obtaining a new product (secondary text) is possible only on condition of the student's permanent communication with the author of the original text, student's staying in a kind of indirect dialogue with him [16, p. 193].

IV. CONCLUSION

The aim of practical training is threefold – educational-developmental-upbringing. As the authors of the manual “Workshop on methods of teaching linguistic subjects in high school” correctly claim, learning objective involves acquiring the theory, elaborating a system of subject and speech skills. Developmental aim is realized when mastering the experience of the search, creative activity, it provides the development of the skills of transferring knowledge and skills into a new situation based on the problem and search activity, linguistic intuition, phonetic and intonation hearing, logical presentation of ideas, intellectual and cognitive abilities (audio and visual, operational and long-term memory, voluntary and involuntary attention, imagination, etc.), psychological readiness to communicate in different situations. The upbringing goal is realized by selection of the educational material (texts, illustrations, pictures, situations, etc.), which reflects universal moral values. Didactic material should be directed to the developing national consciousness, understanding the laws of their native language and society, associated with the leading ideas of philology, which allows students to understand the history of the language development, to master the richness of its expressive means [11, p. 109].

Development of text-formation competency should be continued during the seminars, which is an important form of learning organization in higher educational institutions and provides the development of professional thinking, cognitive motivation and professional use of knowledge in educational conditions [2, p. 179]. If during practical classes analytical and synthetic work with the text dominates, students' speech during seminars is the result of methodically properly organized preparatory work: based on the written notes, abstracts and thematic notes to create their own text – speech in front of the audience or participating in debates and discussions.

During seminars students acquire knowledge about the diversity and variety of academic genres – abstract, theses of article, article summaries, review, article and so on. Analysis of these genres makes it possible to focus future navigators' attention on general genre and stylistic characteristics of texts, to acquaint them with the typical speech clichés, compression, text folding up techniques.

Thus, methodically appropriate selection of learning forms, adequate to the content allows improving future navigators' ability to take notes, review, annotate texts, which provides developing text formation competency.

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